

WORD FORMATION WAYS IN ENGLISH

A.V. Rustamzadeh

Doctor of Philosophy in Philology, Azerbaijan University of Languages, Chair of English
Grammar

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15484030>

Abstract. *The article deals with the word formation ways in English. It introduces language as a constantly moving and developing system. The article mentions that language belongs to society, there is no society without language, and there is no language without society. With this claim it points out the importance of the language. Then the article highlights the creation of new words over times. The article reveals that new words are created due to the internal capabilities of languages or due to borrowings from other languages, and enrich the vocabulary of the language. New words are reported to have been formed at all stages of language history in the article. The article also specifically emphasizes that the emergence of a number of new words in the English language is associated with the names of specific individuals such as J. Chaucer, W. Shakespeare, and others. Word creation is presented as one of the important areas of linguistics in the article. The methods of word formation have been identified in the article as well. Some information on the types of word formation in English such as “affixation, conversion, and the formation of compound words” have been touched upon widely in the article as well.*

Keywords: *word, formation, create, new, conversion, compound, affix.*

INTRODUCTION

Language is a constantly moving and developing system. It is clear that language belongs to society, there is no society without language, and there is no language without society. The development and change in society naturally cannot but have its impact on language. Every language develops over time, new words are created. These new words are created due to the internal capabilities of languages or due to borrowings from other languages, and enrich the vocabulary of the language.

The enrichment of vocabulary is one of the main factors in the development of a language. The lexicon of a language - that is, words and their meanings - is constantly changing and updating. This change is an indicator that the language is alive and dynamic. With the development of society and the emergence of new technologies, new words and expressions are created. For example, as a result of new inventions, scientific discoveries and social changes, concepts that did not exist before or were expressed differently are expressed with new words.

The problem of the emergence and use of new words has long been one of the topics that linguists put their interests on. Especially in our modern era, due to the fact that the language is more free and dynamic, the increase in the number of new words entering the language is striking. One of the characteristics of this era is that the language is moving away from previous restrictions and is more open to innovations and changes. As a result, many new words and expressions are emerging in various fields, for example, technology, culture, social life, etc.

The scientific novelty of the research lies in the analysis of morphological, semantic and lexical mechanisms of word formation in the English language and the study of the relationship of these mechanisms with social and technological changes. In particular, the study of the process of

entering the language of new terms arising under the influence of the Internet and social media increases the special importance of this study. Also, the ways in which newly formed words enter the lexical system and the impact of this process on the evolution of the language are more precisely determined.

MAIN PART

English is a very productive language. Today it is considered one of the most widely spoken languages in the world. D. Crystal writes: “Although English is the most widely spoken language in the world, it is second only to Chinese (Mandarin) in terms of the number of speakers and currently, more than 427 million people speak English in the world” [Crystal 1988, p.289].

There are two ways in which English is accepted as a global language by other countries: it is established as an official language and is considered the first official language in education. In some cases, it is established as a second language with a separate article in the constitution. English has been accepted as a language with a special status in 70 countries of the world. Among them are the names of countries such as Ghana, Nigeria, Singapore, India, etc. In this respect, English is far ahead of other languages - French, German, Spanish and Arabic.

English is taught as a foreign language in 100 countries around the world. English is taught as the main foreign language in China, Russia, Spain, Egypt, and Brazil, as well as in Azerbaijan itself.

New words can be formed at all stages of the history of the language. The emergence of a number of new words in the English language is associated with the names of specific individuals. J. Chaucer introduced a large number of words into the English language and also created hundreds of new words. W. Shakespeare is also known for creating new words in the English language [Potter 2014, p. 56].

Word creation is considered to be one of the important areas of linguistics and the following methods are defined:

1. Word formation by adding various suffixes to the root of the word; (teacher, kindness)
2. Word formation by adding a word to the root of the word; (sunlight, toothbrush)
3. Word formation by changing the word from one part of speech to another; (visit, talk)
4. Word formation by giving a new meaning to the word (mouse, web).

A. Akhundov writes that since different languages have different suffixes, word formation is observed in different types [Akhundov 1988, p.90]:

- a) prefixed;
- b) suffixed;
- c) internal suffixed.

It is also possible for a word to be formed as a result of the presence of various suffixes, such as prefixes, infixes and postfixes. English is an inflectional language with an analytical language structure, and this type of word formation is very common in English. Words formed by adding a suffix to the root of a word are called inflectional words. Creating a word by adding a word to the root of a word belongs to syntactically formed word formation. There are two types of syntactically formed words:

a) Compound words formed by combining two words. Examples of compound nouns that form nouns in English are: plum tree “plum tree”, (noun+noun); verbs: browbeat “to frighten” (verb+verb);

- b) Compound words formed by combining three or more words.

There are types of word formation in English such as affixation, conversion, and the formation of compound words.

Prefixes are considered suffixes that are added to the beginning of a word. For example:
-mono, -multi, -post, -un are words formed by adding prefixes:

The English language is considered to be quite rich in prefixes.

Suffixes are affixes added to the end of a word. C.C. Frays writes in his work “The Structure of the English Language” that the main purpose of suffixes is to indicate the class to which a word belongs. For example, suffixes that form nouns, suffixes that form adjectives, etc. [Fries 1952, p.39].

Let’s give some examples of suffixes according to some parts of speech:

<i>Suffixes</i>	<i>Examples</i>
<i>-ism</i> (noun-forming suffix)	<i>terrorism</i>
<i>-dom</i> (noun-forming suffix)	<i>freedom</i>
<i>-er</i> və <i>-or</i> noun-forming suffixes.	<i>employer</i>

The suffixes *-er* and *-or* mainly create words denoting art.

<i>-en</i> və <i>-ify</i> (verb-forming suffixes)	<i>widen simplify</i>
<i>-able</i> (adjective-forming suffix)	<i>reasonable</i> <i>unprofitable</i>
<i>-ly</i> (productive suffix that forms an adverb)	<i>unhappily naturally</i>

The transfer of word formation from one part of speech to another is widespread in languages without word-modifying suffixes. This method of word formation is called conversion. Conversion cannot be limited to a syntactic phenomenon such as the use of parts of speech as different members of a sentence. It can be defined as only one type of conversion. The following types of conversion have been identified: *substantivization, adjectivalization, pronominalization, verbalization, adverbialization, conjunctionalization* [Girard 2007, p.82].

F.R. Palmer notes that conversion can also be observed when a proper noun becomes a common noun [Palmer 1969, p.116]. For example:

Did you see my Dickens?

The proper noun Dickens used in this sentence has been converted to a common noun in the sense of book.

Based on research, we can conclude that conversion is observed at 4 levels: *syntactic, morphological-syntactic, semantic-syntactic, semantic* [Akhundov 1988, p.160].

The conversion related to the phenomena of substantivization and adjectivalization is called semantic-syntactic conversion. In this case, words with noun-adjective homonymy can be used syntactically in the place of a noun or an adjective. For example, in compounds such as *a stone wall, an iron gate*, the first part retains its true meaning, and syntactically adjectivalization is observed here. In compounds such as *a stone heart, an iron wrist*, the first parts do not retain their literary meanings, depending on the syntactic-semantic environment [Stekauer 1996, p.67].

Semantic conversion occurs when a word belonging to one part of speech loses all its semantic and grammatical connections with that part of speech and moves to a new part of speech. It should be emphasized that semantic conversion is fundamentally different from the other three types. While the three methods we have discussed are based on the relationship of word formation with grammar, the fourth method is related to the semantics of word formation.

Every day, new words are created in the language and enter the vocabulary of the language. Most of such words are considered lexicalized words. When creating new words in the language, various word formation methods are used. Some of them are very dominant from a lexical point of view. For example, the formation of compound, compound words and their use in the language are very common. When creating new words in the language, borrowing from other languages, shortening, combining words, using parts of speech in different ways, etc. can be observed. These methods of word formation are widely used in the language. Observations show that in the future, the use of words created through conversion will be more dominant. S.Martsa writes that in the future, words created through conversion in English will make up most of the vocabulary of the language [Martsa 2013, p.115]. Since many nouns and verbs in English refer to the same concept, conversion is widely used in this language.

Conversion is considered as the process of a word belonging to different classes without adding any suffix. For example: while *sign* can be used as a noun, *sign* can also be used as a verb, and this process is called a conversion event. H. Marchand writes that the easy conversion of words in a language cannot be observed in all cases [Marchand 1967, p.22]. For example, the words *mind* and *matter* are considered to be such words.

Since nouns and verbs have the same root, conversion is a common phenomenon in English. P. Stekauer writes that this phenomenon is not observed in languages with grammatical gender, such as Latin, Greek, etc. [Stekauer 1996, p. 55].

Currently, the status of the word conversion is somewhat unclear. While some attribute conversion to word creation, others consider it a new branch of word creation. L. Bauer writes that conversion should be considered a new direction in language [Bauer 1983, p.32].

L.Bauer argues that conversion is an easier way of word formation, so it will be used more in the future in English [Bauer 1983, p.15]. It is very difficult to observe how many converted words are used in everyday speech. Of course, we will see how this process develops in the future.

The term conversion, which is the process of using a word in a language as a different part of speech (without taking any suffixes), is also somewhat dubious and not entirely accurate. Conversion is derived from the word converted (shifted) and is considered to be a word that more clearly reflects the process of such word formation in a language [Girard 2007, p.155].

During conversion, a word can be used in relation to different parts of speech. In this process, “zero-word modification” is observed and words can only be used in different forms in a transferred form. That is, in this case, the word is converted into another part of speech without receiving any suffixes [Twardzisz 1997, p.156]. However, although this is not observed externally, there is a change in grammatical meaning. For this reason, another term for this process is “functional change”.

As we mentioned above, conversion is considered very productive in English, which is associated with its easier word formation than other means. L. Bauer writes that “Conversion is a completely free word formation process and can be converted into any word class as needed” [Bauer 1983, p.83]. This means that any word can belong to another class, in particular, nouns can be easily converted into verbs, and verbs into nouns, and there are no morphological restrictions here. However, it should be noted that derivational nouns can rarely be subject to conversion (with the exception of derivational verbs). L. Bauer writes that this exception is understandable. If there is already a word in the language, the creation of a new word for the same concept will naturally be suppressed and eliminated as an obstacle in terms of language economy [Bauer 1983, p.90]. For example: the noun *denial* can never be used as a verb, because this word was formed from the

verb deny. In this case, the lack of conversion is explained by the fact that both words, although belonging to different parts of speech, have the same meaning and there is no need for them to replace one another. For example, we can give the words sign and to sign as an example. The word signal can be converted to the word to signal, because there is a slight semantic difference in their meaning [Bauer 1983, p. 226].

It should be noted that the conversion process also had a semantic limitation. The converted word only contains one of the many meanings of the original word. For example, the word paper has many meanings: newspaper, material to wrap things, etc.

R.Driven and G.Radden write that the purpose of conversion can vary depending on the purpose of the users [Driven 2007, p.10]. The reason why adults prefer conversion is that they try to use fewer words when speaking or writing. The reason why children prefer conversion is that they tend to convert in order to express themselves more clearly. However, they also make more grammatical errors. In any case, the use of conversion makes communication easier.

H. Marchand suggests the conditions for the formation of original and modified words [Marchand 1967, p.13]. Forms that condition the conversion:

- a) semantic dependence (a word that reflects the meaning of another word is considered a derivative word);
- b) degree of use (a less frequently used word is considered a converted word);
- c) degree of semantic use (a word that has less semantic meaning is considered a converted word);
- d) phonetic change (there are some suffixes that can reflect the word class to which the concept belongs);

The next type of word formation is called compounding (composition). In this case, two or more words are combined to form a new word. For example, in English, the compound noun backache can be formed from the combination of the nouns back and ache. Or post+card=postcard.

Conversion of compound words can be found in many parts of speech. The most common compound conversions are the following:

Conversion of compound nouns:

Car park “car park”, rock band “rock band”, etc.;

Conversion of compound adjectives:

Heart-breaking “heartbreaking”, sugar-free “sugar-free”, airsick “airsickness due to air travel”;

Conversion of compound verbs:

Oven-bake “to bake in the oven”, baby-sit “to babysit”, chain-smoke “to smoke chain”;

Conversion of adverbs: Good-naturedly, nevertheless, etc.

In complex conversions, some words are hyphenated, while others are not. Some complex words are written separately, while others are written together. To know these correctly, it is necessary to refer to dictionaries as this type of writing has already been accepted in a stable form in the vocabulary of the language.

The form of forming a noun from an adjective also has wide possibilities for word formation in modern English. In this case, the adjective takes on all the features of a noun, that is, it can take the indefinite article like a noun, it takes the suffix -(e)s in the plural, etc. The example may be given like this: *An aborigine, aborigines, aborigine's; a liberal, liberals, liberal's* və s.

The example is written to present how adjectives function as nouns in sentence structure:

1) *Please light the fire and have a warm.*

2) *Brave innocents!*

3) *I am one of your familiars.*

Incompletely noun-form words from adjectives do not accept all the properties of nouns. They only accept the definite article (the). Therefore, they retain many of the properties of adjectives. For example:

the old, the young, the poor, the rich, the blind, the mute, the deaf, and so on.

As can be seen, the word formation formed in this way mainly reflects the type belonging to a certain class: the young = young people, the wounded = wounded soldiers.

It should be noted that such nouns can also refer to the singular, for example, the deceased “changed his world”, the departed “marhum”, the accused “tried”, the deserted “thrown away” the condemned “condemned”.

CONCLUSION

The most productive word-forming processes in English are affixation, compounding, and conversion. In morphology, productivity refers to the degree to which a word-forming process is used in a language.

The process of word formation in English is carried out through numerous methods and techniques. According to the results of the study, the most productive methods of word formation are affixation and compounding. These methods are the most widespread and play a key role in the development of the language. Affixation is of particular importance in the formation of new words, because by adding prefixes and suffixes, words acquire new meanings. Compounding, on the other hand, allows different words to combine to create new concepts and creates the conditions for the formation of numerous new terms in the English language.

Conversion and abbreviation methods, while applied in some cases, contribute to the economic and rapid development of the language, but these methods are considered less productive. Although these methods are applied in certain cases and in limited areas, they do not have a great impact on the general development of the language and the creation of new words. These methods are used more in specific situations and in informal language, therefore they do not have the ability to spread widely.

REFERENCES

1. Akhundov, A. General linguistics. / A.Akhundov. – Baku: Maarif, – 1988. – 272 p.
2. Bauer, L. English word-formation. Cambridge textbooks in Linguistics. / L.Bauer. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, – 1983. – 311 p.
3. Crystal, D. The English Language. / D.Crystal. – UK: Penguin Books, – 1988. – 312 p.
4. Fries, Ch.C. The Structure of English. / Ch.C.Fries. – New York: York Press, – 1952. – 304 p.
5. Driven, R. Cognitive English Grammar. / R.Driven, G.Radden. – US: John Benjamins Pub., – 2007. – 374 p.
6. Girard, R. Evolution and Conversion. / R.Girard [et al.] – New York: A and C Black, – 2007. – 282 p.
7. Martsa, S. Conversation in English: cognitive semantic approach. / S.Martsa. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, – 2013. – 304 p.
8. Marchand, H. Expansion, transposition and derivation [Text] // La linguistique. – 1967. № 1. – P. 13-26.

9. Nordquist, R. Understanding the Types of Verbs in English: [Electronic resource] / ThoughtCo, – Apr. 5, – 2023. URL: [thoughtco.com/verb-definition-1692592](https://www.thoughtco.com/verb-definition-1692592).
10. Palmer, F.H. Grammar of spoken English. / F.H.Palmer. –Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, – 1969. – 341 p.
11. Potter, S. Dilimiz. / İngilis dilindən tərcümə etdilər: F.Y.Veysəlli, S.B.Mustafayeva. – Bakı, – 2014. – 167 s.
12. Poutsma, H. A Grammar of Late Modern English. / H.Poutsma. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, – 1914. – 524 p.
13. Stekauer, P. A Theory of conversion in English. / P.Stekauer. – UK: P.Lang, – 1996. – 155 p
14. Twardzisz, P. Zero derivation in English. / P.Twardzisz. – Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Marii Curie-Skłodowskiej, – 1997. – 208 p.